

<p align="center">GENERAL CHARACTERISTICS OF THE TERMS, WHICH MEAN THE MARK</p>		<p align="center">Literature</p> <p>Keywords: subject, sign, integral, differential, core, auxiliary, marginal, terminological meaning, lexicographic interpretation, logical relation and grammatical relation.</p>
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<p align="center">Abstract</p>	<p>Apparently, the term symbols occupy a special place in terminology, with a certain amount. However, they do not always receive special attention in terminology. The role of symbolic terms in the Uzbek terminological system has not been fully evaluated. There is also a need to clarify their logical and grammatical relationship with the connecting words. Differentiation of the leadership and auxiliary functions of the symbolic terms is important, first and foremost, in distinguishing between the general and the private, integral and differential features of the symbolic terms, as well as the terminosystem in general. This, in the end, plays an important role in improving lexicographic interpretations.</p>
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The nominative function of terms does not have an absolute social meaning, the choice of their nomenclature (phonetic form) arises from the need for some language users to understand and understand the text on which it is based. Therefore, a clear definition of the rigid position of the term in the system of the general system will provide an in-depth analysis of the semantic nature of the term, while the use of the differential-semantic method at the highest level will ensure the feasibility of this possibility. In other words, the development and implementation of the semantic analysis methodology, which helps to unambiguously and clearly disclose the semantic content of each term, further increases the need for terminology selection.

The term symbols occupy a special place in terminology, with a certain amount. However, they are not always of particular interest in terminology. There are several reasons for this:

- 1) The number of symbols is less than the number of terms that denote the subject;
- 2) The terms symbols are more likely to have a composite relationship with the subject terms;
- 3) Since the notion of “character” is related to the notion of “subject”, the emphasis is on the notion of “subject” and both types of terms are associated with a determinant + definitive relationship and form a complex name, expression (“descript”) in the language;
- 4) Because appellate texts are often identifiable and identifiable, this also acts as a stereotype in terms of symbolic terms, and so on.

Terminological research today focuses on the new aspects of the study object. Some studies focus more on the term “original” in terms of the term “original”, while in others, the word “word” attracts attention, and the semantic and formal features of the term are analyzed as in ordinary words [1].

The terms used in terms of terms such as "accuracy", "systematic", "emotional neutrality" are characterized by their arbitrary use at first sight, and thus stand out from other grammatical categories. Although, "terms are words limited by their special purpose; words striving to be

unambiguous as an exact expression of concepts and the name of things by AA Reformatsky, although it is in every sense compatible with the definition of "[2], the objective approach to the designation of characters is as if their "impracticality in application" is shadowed. Because of the linguist's definition of the term "burden of understanding" in terms of definitions, the attribute "darkens" the meaning of the term, to a certain degree, in this context [3]. As mentioned earlier, a significant difference in the degree of visibility and applicability of the terms of the subject and the character is reinforced. Hence, it is clear that the linguistic semantic-grammatical features of the symbolic terms require special study.

When using symbolic terms, two things should be considered:

1) The use of a symbolic term with a unit that is a term: 1. **Ballistik** raketa qanotli raketadan **aerodinamik** ko'tarish kuchi hosil qiluvchi sirtining yo'qligi bilan farqlanadi ("O'zME"). 2. Chortoq mineral vannasini qabul silgandan keyin qattiq og'riq paydo bo'ldi.. **balneologik** reaksiya yuz berdi ("Fan va turmush"). 3. ...**barometrik** bosimning kamayishi organizm hayot faoliyatining anchagina izdan chiqishiga sabab bo'ladi ("Fan va turmush"). 4. Shu narsa aniqki, ocherkning... ba'zi namunalari xikoya va qissa kabi sof **belletristik** janr namunalari o'xshaydi ("Sharq yulduzi").

2) The use of a symbolic term with a non-term unit: 1. Shuning uchun ham hozirda qishloq xo'jaligida band bo'lgan ortiqcha mehnat qiluvchilarni sanoatga, xizmat ko'rsatish sohasiga jalb qilish **agrar** siyosatimizning g'oyat muhim yo'nalishidir (Gazetadan). 2. Xastalikni keltirib chiqargan "sababchi allergen"ni maxsus **allergologik** tekshirish uslubi bilan aniqlab olamiz (Gazetadan). 3. **Dialogik** nutqda qaraganda monologda gaplar ko'proq mustaqillikka egadir (O'TA). 4. Ma'lumki, odamlarning geografik ob'ektlarni nomlash tajribasida shu joylarning **geomorfologik** xususiyatlari muhim va asosiy belgilardan hisoblangan ("O'TA"). 5. Murakkab qurilish ishlarida, ko'mir va ma'dan qazishda, shuningdek, **gidrotexnik** ishlarda tebranma harakat asqotadi ("Fan va turmush"). 6. Aytish mumkinki, bu voqea xavfli qurollanish poygasiga turtki berib, nafaqat mintaqaviy, balki yana **global** oqibatlariga olib kelishi mumkin (Gazetadan).

The first series uses **ballistik** term with *raketa*, **aerodinamik** term with *ko'tarish kuchi*, **balneologik** term with *reaksiya*, **barometrik** term with *bosim*, **belletristik** term with *janr* terms are used, in the second group **agrar**, **allergologik**, **dialogik**, **geomorfologik**, **gidrotexnik**, **global** words are used with the terms *siyosat*, *tekshirish*, *nutq*, *xususiyat*, *ishlar*, *oqibat*. The works were eventually used in conjunction with the words of the general public – they became determinants.

In the use of symbolic terms, the term can also be used as one of the core or marginal status. In a nuclear position, it is seen to be controlled by another term. Examples: 1. *Bizningcha, endi mamlakatimizning intellektual salohiyatini yuksaltirish hamda xalq xo'jaligining turli sohalarida malakali mutaxassislar tayyorlab borish maqsadida iste'dodli yoshlarni aniqlash...* (Tafakkur). 2. *Quyosh energiyasidan foidalanish hisobiga yonilg'i-energetika resurslari sarfining kamayishi xalq xo'jaligiga juda ko'p iqtisodiy samara beradi* (Gazetadan). 3. **Kibernetik** tizimlar bir-biridan

ularida harakatlanuvchi signallar oqimining tabiatiga qarab farq qiladi. (“O‘zME”). 4. Bular garchi qisman oldingi tarix kitoblaridan **kompilyatsiya** tarzida tuzilgan bo‘lsa-da, ularda Qo‘qon xonligining 1843 yildan 1875 yilgacha bo‘lgan tarixiga oid qimmatli ma‘lumotlar bor (“O‘TA”). 5. Urug‘lik chigitning vil‘tga chidamli yangi navlarini, shuningdek, yuksak **texnologik** sifatlarga ega bo‘lgan chigitni ekish ancha ko‘paytirildi. (Gazetadan). Although the terms 'category' in these discourses are logically core, referring to *salohiyat*, *resurs*, *tizim*, *tarz*, *sifat*, the logical emphasis of these terms and the impossibility of replacing dominant words are a core component.

1. There are cases where the terms "sign" can be used in the extreme, not in the core. Examples: 1. *Yuqorida ko‘rsatib o‘tilgan huquq buzuvchilik hollarini sodir etgan shaxslarga nisbatan ma‘muriy jazo bilan bir qatorda, intizomiy jazo chorasi ham qo‘llanishi mumkin* (Gazetadan). 2. *Toshkent memorial yodgorliklari yana bir monumental san‘at asari bilan boyidi. Gazetadan.* 3. *Toshkent kimyo-texnologiya institutining konstruktorlik byurosi polimer isitkichlar yaratdi (“Fan va turmush”).* 4. *Bir koordinata sistemasidan ikkinchi koordinata sistemasiga o‘tish sferik trigonometriya formulalari yordamida amalga oshiriladi (O‘zME).* 5. *Yaponiyada va Amerikaning g‘arbiy qirg‘oqlarida sodir bo‘ladigan zilzilalarda ham tektonik, ham vulkanik kuchlar baravariga ishtirok qiladi* (Gazetadan).

The above examples show both logical and grammatical inconsistencies. It has been observed that the unit of logic may be subordinated simultaneously grammatically. Also, the term grammatically subordinate "sign" may have a secondary function, not logic. In the terms used to indicate this sign, the symbolic meaning must either be increased or diminished, and should therefore be regarded as a change in subjective meanings. When a word is used with a common term (appellate) language, the emphasis is often on the term, and it is used with special logical emphasis, which is logically superior to the word in its definition. One of the grammatical peculiarities of the symbolic terms is that they are relative and not degree, even though they are of adjective sense.

Most of the terms used in the designation are determined by several factors:

1) Many of the terms included in this category are terms of use and many are derived from European languages;

2) The semantic accuracy of the terms implies their non-degree. Words that come from the sign as a component of a compositional term can also be used to verbalize certain aspects of a complex concept. Examples: **termoelektrik** (hodisa), **fizioterapevtik** (usuli); **elektrotexnik** (sanoat), **avtoremont** (ishxonasi), **agrobiologik** (tadqiqotlar), **aerodinamik** (laboratoriya), **biokimyoviy** (jarayonlar); **biofizik** (tadqiqotlar); **geokimyoviy** (jarayonlar); **geomorfologik** (xususiyatlar); **geofizik** (omillar) and etc.

There are also double terms, each of which is made up of nuclear, in other words logically equivalents:

jinoiy-prosessual (jinoiy-prosessual kodeks)
madaniy-maishiy (madaniy-maishiy xizmat)
ma'naviy-ma'rifiy (ma'naviy-ma'rifiy tadbirlar)
makroiqtisodiy (makroiqtisodiy siyosat)
ommaviy-madaniy (ommaviy-madaniy ishlar)
ommaviy-siyosiy (ommaviy-siyosiy ishlar)
sosial-demokratik (sosial-demokratik qarashlar)

The terminology of the common vocabulary occurs when its meaning is multiplied or derivative. For this reason, terms that are completely absorbed in a language, and many of the terms that appear in that language, are meaningless. This also applies to terms that directly represent the sign. For example, in the “Explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language”, the word is given **sirtqi** as follows:

1) the outer, outer surface of an object or person; surface, outer: *Binoning ichki va sirtqi tomoni. Sirtqi ko'rinish. Sirtqi dori.* Common names of drugs that cannot be swallowed or consumed (such as eye drops, ulcers, etc.);

2) to study without attending school. *Sirtqi o'qish. Sirtqi ta'lim. Institutning sirtqi bo'limi. Vahobjon o'tgan yilning avgustida sirtqi institutga imtihon topshirgani Toshkentga tushgan edi.* (S.Ahmad, Tog' afsonasi) [4, 525].

The second meaning of the word is terminological, and the similarity (metaphorization) is the basis for the formation of this essence. In the first sense, lexeme has an appealing meaning, and the concept of 'learning outside of the educational institution' has a terminological meaning in the form of 'education without going to school'.

In this sense, the term *badiiy* symbol is distinguished by its complex semantics:

1) Expressing the truth through elegant means, techniques, images; illustrator: *Badiiy adabiyot. Badiiy asar. Badiiy san'at. Badiiy fil'm. Badiiy adabiyotning zamiri hayotdir.* (X.Yodgorov, Hayot to'liqlari). *Elmurod badiiy asarlar odamlarning tashna dillariga naqadar rohat bag'ishlaganini sezar, lekin bunday asarlarning o'z tilimizda kamligidan kuyinar edi* (P.Tursun, O'qituvchi).

2) Belongs to literary: *Badiiy mahorat. Badiiy tasvir. Badiiy tafakkur. Badiiy did. Badiiy salohiyat. Ijodda faqat niyatning o'zi kifoya qilmaydi, shunga yarasha badiiy salohiyat va teran fikr ham zarur* (Gazetadan). *Badiiy fikr o'zining shakli bilan tug'iladi* (U. Normatov, Talant tarbiyasi).

3) activities related to artistic activity: *Badiiy rahbar. Badiiy havaskorlar to'garagi. Badiiy jamoa. Badiiy muhit. Badiiy havaskorlik to'garagi repetisiya qilayotir* (P.Tursun, O'qituvchi). *O'zbekistonlik badiiy kollektivlar va ijrochilarnshg konsertlarida oltmish mingdan ortiq kishi*

hozir bo'ldi (Gazetadan). Yangi insonni voyaga yetkazish va tarbiyalashda ijtimoiy va badiiy muhitning roli katta (Gazetadan) [5].

The three distinctive meanings highlighted in the dictionary article are:

in the first meaning: *adabiyot, asar, san'at, fil'm* сўзлари;

in the second meaning: *mahorat, did, salohiyat, fikr* сўзлари;

in the third meaning: *to'garak, jamoa, muhit* сўзлари

It is thought that at first glance it seems as if only the compounds are exchanged, and that the meaning of the word changes. But the primary means of distinguishing these meanings is the distinction element in the first sense, the word "image", in the second sense, "belonging" and in the third sense, the term "touch".

There are some controversial points in this statement. They are:

- 1) all three meanings are terminological;
- 2) the lexicographic interpretation does not reflect the sign;
- 3) illustrative examples are not sourced from industry sources.

It is noteworthy that in the vocabulary article, in all three terms, the term is used as a symbol:

in the first meaning: *-(u)vchi* affix;

in the second meaning: *tegishli, mansub* adjectives;

in the third meaning: *oid* auxiliary.

These three elements have the potential to make the term expressive more expressive.

In the first sense, the term literary designation serves as an auxiliary feature in the combination of fiction and fiction, and it is also based on the fact that the term is not a logical emphasis. In the second and third sense, this term assumes the function of a compound nuclear. This is determined by the fact that the above signs of nuclear quality are manifested in these applications.

It has already been mentioned that the lexemes in appellate application are less important than the terminological derivatives. It is noted that not all terminals derived from other languages are included in the Uzbek language, but not all. Here are some examples:

ANTIQA:

1. *esk. Ancient, belonging to ancient. U [Iskandar] endi devor g'ishtlarini buzib, antiqa belgilarini yigitlarga uzatar ekan.. xumcha ochilib borgani sari yuragidagi g'ulg'ula ham ortar edi. (M.Mansurov, Yombi).*

2. Жуда қойил, ҳайратга соладиган. *Ota-murod oddiy bodring, pomidorlarni turli usullarda qirqib, antiqa salatlar tayyorlar.. Zulxumor bo'lsa, uning bu san'atiga mahliyo bo'lib o'tirar edi.* (M.Mansurov, Yombi). «Do'stlik» mehmonxonasigacha bo'lgan masofa-ni erinmay bosib o'tsangiz, antiqa bozorga duch kelasiz. Gazetadan[6].

At the same time, the meaning of "high-grade snowflake skin" has a third meaning, that is, an independent terminological meaning that must be described separately.

ARABIY:

esk.Arabic, Arabic Language and Literature; Arabic. *Arabiy adabiyot. Yana o'sha arabiy va forsiy iboralar to'la, biz tushunmaydigan mashaqqatli o'qishga sho'ng'ib ketdik* (M.Muhammadjonov, Turmush urinishlari) [7].

This term represents the terminological essence of the symbol in the Arabic noun combination.

AXLOQIY:

Belonging to moral. *Axloqiy prinsiplar. Bir vaqtlar bu uyga onasi bilan mehmon bo'lib kelgan bir tatar qizi ruscha bir axloqiy romanni unutib qoldirgan.* (Oybek, Tanlangan asarlar) [8].

The combination of ethical principles is the terminological essence of the lexeme, which is a symbol.

BAHORG:

1. For spring, spring, springtime. *Bahorgi ekinlar. Bahorgi toshkin. Bahorgi beg'amlik — kuzgi pushaymonlik.*Maqol. *Bahorgi harakat — kuzgi barakat (Maqol) Navro'zi olam o'lkamizga tashrif buyurgandan beri, barcha bog'larda bahorgi ishlar kizib ketdi.* (Gazetadan).

2. ayn. баҳори. *Bahorgi ekinlar. Bahorgi g'alla* [9].

The second meaning of the lexeme is terminological, with the need to put the lexicographical mark "agricultural". The need for such lexicographic complementarities can be seen in both religious and secular expressions. It is worth noting that the interpretations of the religious word "religious, spiritual", reflect the pure terminological interpretations of the secular word "real, material world, life, life".

References

1. Vinokur G.O. Grammaticheskie nablyudeniya v oblasti tehnikeskoy terminologii // Trudi MIIFLI. – M., 1939. T. 5. – S. 3–54;
2. Reformatskiy A. A. Termin kak chlen leksicheskoy sistemi yazika // Problemi strukturnoy lingvistiki. M., 1967. S. 110–111.
3. Alimuradov. O. A. Osobennosti strukturi i funkcionirovaniya otraslevix terminosistem (na primere terminosistemi nanotexnologiy) / O. A. Alimuradov, M. N. Latu, A. V. Razduev. Pyatigorsk, 2011. 112 s.
4. O‘TIL “O‘zbekiston milliy ensiklopediyasi” Davlat ilmiy nashriyoti, 2007.3-jild 525 s)
5. O‘TIL “O‘zbekiston milliy ensiklopediyasi” Davlat ilmiy nashriyoti, 2007.3-jild 525 s
6. O‘TIL “O‘zbekiston milliy ensiklopediyasi” Davlat ilmiy nashriyoti, 2007.3-jild 525 s
7. O‘TIL “O‘zbekiston milliy ensiklopediyasi” Davlat ilmiy nashriyoti, 2007.3-jild 525 s
8. O‘TIL “O‘zbekiston milliy ensiklopediyasi” Davlat ilmiy nashriyoti, 2007.3-jild 525 s
9. O‘TIL “O‘zbekiston milliy ensiklopediyasi” Davlat ilmiy nashriyoti, 2007.3-jild 525